

The product development as determinant factor of the operational model in the production line in an automobile industry assembly line

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Abstract

The alteration of the operational model used by the employee in one phase of the process in an automobile industry is determinant factor of the work conditions, product design and its physical and dimensional characteristics. Throughout this study it was pointed that the standardization of the operational model utilized by the worker has direct influence on the physical conditions and physical effort during the execution of the tasks and the strategy adopted by the worker to accomplish the production time goals. The product design change and the insertion of the new products in the assembly line has direct influence on the operational model utilized by the worker during the execution the new tasks. Throughout the observation of one phase in the assembly line of one automobile industry using the Ergonomics Analyses Method. It was compared the type of the operational model in the same activity with the purpose to evidence of the ergonomics risks according to the postural position utilized by the worker. With this comparison it was possible to indicate which is the best postural position for the worker for the execution of the tasks, with more comfort without loss of productivity.